

DESCRIPTION, DIDACTIC REQUIREMENTS AND CONDITIONS OF SUBJECTS THAT DEVELOP STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES RELATED TO GENERAL PROFESSIONAL SUBJECTS

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Abstract. Creativity is one of the most used and valued skills in the 21st century. It is important to develop creativity to achieve effective and high-level education. In the development of creative ability, the description of various subjects, didactic requirements, conditions and personal characteristics of human nature are studied. In this article, specific descriptions are given based on the above-mentioned approaches to the study of creativity.

Keywords: creativity, different thinking, thinking skills, educational process, higher qualification, subjects that teach creativity.

ОПИСАНИЕ, ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЯ И УСЛОВИЯ ПРЕДМЕТОВ, РАЗВИВАЮЩИХ ТВОРЧЕСКИЕ СПОСОБНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ, ОТНОСЯЩИЕСЯ К ОБЩЕПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫМ ПРЕДМЕТАМ

Аннотация. Креативность является одним из наиболее используемых и ценных навыков в 21 веке. Важно развивать креативность для достижения эффективного и высокого уровня образования. В развитии творческих способностей изучаются описание различных предметов, дидактические требования, условия и личностные особенности человеческой натуры. В данной статье даны конкретные описания на основе упомянутых выше подходов к изучению креативности.

Ключевые слова: креативность, иное мышление, мыслительные способности, учебный процесс, высшая квалификация, предметы, обучающие творчеству.

INTRODUCTION

Creativity is one of the most valued learning skills in the 21st century. Creativity is understood as the ability to think at a higher level based on complex and post-formal thinking related to the creation of new and valuable ideas. Higher-order thinking is the ability to think competently and strategically, and these skills should include critical, creative, and metacognitive thinking. In addition, today it is important to develop creativity to achieve effective and high-level education. Creativity is a concept specific to human development and personality. It begins to develop from the first years of school and then continues in higher education. The number of human experiences in life and the activities of teachers help to increase creativity. Therefore, it is important to develop educational programs for the development of creativity skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to scientists, creativity is not just another skill, but a complex process of human subjectivity, which is based on a set of psychological resources that are specially structured and regulate human behavior. Modern researchers have expanded the concept of creativity, recognizing that creative action is a dynamic and uncertain process and even constitutes a wider social context.

The importance of creativity is increasingly recognized by scientists and specialists in various fields. Research on the development of creativity reminds us that those who do not use creativity in modern society are those who fail in one or more areas of life. While creativity may have been

a luxury for some during the Renaissance, it is now argued that it is a necessity for our survival. Creativity helps people make better use of opportunities and respond more effectively to challenges in their personal and professional lives. Creative behaviors also contribute to quality of life because their expression is often accompanied by feelings of satisfaction and pleasure, which are key elements of emotional well-being and mental health.

In order to support the development of creativity in higher education, it is necessary to promote an institutional culture that attaches great importance to creativity and its manifestation, not limited to traditional forms of scientific development. In this sense, including as one of its elements, it talks about helping teachers to understand and develop their creative abilities and to recognize this as an integral part of their professional skills, as well as teachers' and students' thinking and is to provide an institutional environment that encourages personal development.

RESULTS

The following strategies are offered to university professors and teachers to help create conditions for creativity to flourish in higher education classrooms:

- Having enough time and space in the curriculum to develop students' creative abilities.
- Having enough variety to ensure that all students can be creative.
- Allow students the freedom to work in new and exciting ways.
- Engaging students with real, demanding and interesting work.
- Design assessments that allow for unspecified outcomes.
- Creating a departmental climate that encourages thinking and personal development for staff and students.
- Continuing scholarly debates within the discipline and conversations with various stakeholders about the nature of the subject and the role of creativity in it.

Other recommendations for the development of creativity:

- Taking students' prior knowledge into account.
- Allow time for communication, listen to students with respect.
- Helping students get rid of emotional blocks such as fear of making mistakes and fear of criticism.
- Encourage students to engage in topics that interest them the most.
- Diversification of teaching strategies used in the classroom.
- Give only constructive criticism to students.
- Encourage students to express new ideas.
- Maintain positive relationships with students.
- To promote a psychologically safe environment where students are not afraid to expose themselves.
- Understanding individual differences in behavior and problem-solving skills.

DISCUSSION

It is of particular importance to help teachers develop their creative abilities during their studies, especially during the years of professional training of teachers. This is done not by introducing a single subject on creativity into teacher education curricula, but by creating real creative experiences that prospective teachers experience as students and what they can do as teachers later on. should be done through the teaching and learning environment and they should find ways to express their creative potential.

CONCLUSIONS

Professors and students of higher educational institutions face many problems. The conclusion of the opinions discussed in this article is related to the need to promote a culture of

creativity that encourages the flourishing of creativity among teachers and students. This is especially relevant because the priority models of professional training of teachers are deeply rooted in Uzbek culture, and educational opportunities for creative thinking are still very limited. There are few opportunities for teachers to reflect on their pedagogical practice, participate in dialogue and discuss it. Promoting an environment that promotes active learning and encourages students to use creativity in combination with other skills is a challenge for many university teachers.

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